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Effect of Prey Densities on the Biological Attributes and Predatory Efficiency of *Harmonia Dimidiata* (Fab.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) Feed On *Schizaphis. Graminum* (Rond.) Aphid

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Received Date: 30-Sep-2021

Accepted Date: 22-Oct-2021

Published Date: 31-Oct-2021

Abstract

Research experiments were conducted on the biological attributes of ladybird beetle *Harmonia dimidiata* (Fab.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) at constant prey densities feed on *Schizaphis graminum* aphid at constant temperature (24 ± 1 °C) at Insect Pest Management Program, National Agricultural Research Centre Islamabad.

The effect of six constant prey densities of *S. graminum* aphid was investigated on development, weight, reproductive and predatory efficiency of larvae and adult female *H. dimidiata*. The prey density for larval and adult stages was different. The prey densities for larvae were 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 aphids/day and for adult female beetle the prey density include 40, 80, 120, 160, 200 and 240 aphids/ day. The larvae were maintained till pupation and adult female beetles were maintained from the time of eclosion till their death on constant prey densities. The duration of different larval instars were different at lower prey densities and as the densities increase the duration may become non-significant at higher densities. The pre-oviposition period was significantly different at lower densities and at lowest prey density, 40 aphids /day, the female beetles could not produce eggs, while at higher densities the pre-oviposition period was non-significant different. The oviposition period was also significantly different at lower densities while at higher densities 200 and 240 aphids/ day the oviposition period was non-significant different from each other. The female fecundity was lowest at lower densities and highest at prey density 200 aphids/ day. Once the asymptote level attain by the female beetle then further increase in prey density have non-significant effect on female fecundity. The functional response exhibited by first, second, third and fourth instar larvae exemplified type II with optimum response at a prey density of 40, 60, 80 and 100 aphids/ day respectively. Both the functional and the reproductive numerical response of female beetle showed the upper asymptote level at 200 aphids/ day.

The study highlight the importance of environmental regulation in mass rearing of ladybird beetle *H. dimidiata* for application as a biological control agent against economically important aphid pests of wheat crops in Pakistan.

Keywords: Prey Densities, Biological Attributes, Predatory Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Quantitative and qualitative interactions among various species are essential for managing the pests of agricultural importance. All species in ecosystem is component of composite population and has interaction with numerous other species. The nature of interactions among different species may be competitive, predatory, parasitic or mutualistic (Bellows and Hassell, 1999). The important interaction from biological control point of view is the predator prey relationship in which, how the predators respond to changes in prey densities. Functional response of predator to prey accessibility is of particular interest (Jeschke *et al.*,

2002) and can resolve whether a predator is capable to make conform the population of its prey (Murdoch and Oaten 1975). Functional response is the the number of host insects attacked by an individual bio control agent in relation to host density over a given time period (Solomon 1949). The response is typify by amplify inuantity of prey assault over the smaller prey densities. Upper limit to the quantity of prey attacked at larger prey densities due to satiation in the case of predators (Jeschke *et al.*, 2002). Fundamentally, functional responses are of three types (Holling, 1959). Type I response is typified by a linear increase, type II response by a monotonic slow down the increase and type III response by a sigmoidal increase in the quantity of host attacks. In most insects type II functional response is usually adapted (Begon *et al.*, 1996) also coccinellids (Hodek and Honek, 1996; Dixon, 2000; Agarwala *et al.*, 2009, Jalali *et al.*, 2010). However, predators may demonstrate diverse types of functional response curves according to the functions of host plant (Messina and Hanks, 1998) or prey type (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2007). The same species *Harmonia axyridis* (Pallas) exhibit type I (Lou, 1987), type II (He *et al.*, 1994) and type III (Hu *et al.*, 1989) on unlike aphid species. (Koch *et al.*, 2003), reported that, third instars exhibit type II and adults type I in *H. axyridis* when fed on eggs of monarch butterfly, *Danaus plexippus* (L.)

The objective of this study is to inspect biological parameters and predatory competence of *H. dimidiata* in association with invariable prey densities of *S. graminum* (Rond.) aphid. This study will be helpful for improving our understanding of the predator-prey interactions between *H. dimidiata* and *S. graminum* aphid. This study may be supportive to cost effectively biological control of aphid pests of economic importance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Effect of prey density on the biological attributes and predatory efficiency of immature stages of *H. dimidiata* (Fab.) on *S. graminum* aphid

The experiments were conducted on the consequences of various prey population, on the biological attributes and predatory efficiency of immature stages at constant temperature (24 ± 1 °C), fed on *S. graminum* aphid in growth chamber. The eggs were collected from inside the jars and kept for hatching. Upon hatching first instar larvae were kept singly in plastic rearing vials (6X2) cm and fed on 3rd and 4th instar nymphs of aphids till pupation at constant prey densities (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 aphids/vials on infested wheat leaves. A total of 10 replicates were maintained for each prey density. The fresh weight, growth rate for each immature stages and no of aphids consumed per each larval instars/ day was recorded in each replicates. The process was continued till all the larvae entered in to pupae. The pupae were kept under the same condition for adult emergence.

Effect of prey density on the biological attributes and predatory efficiency of adult female ladybird beetle fed on *S. graminum* aphid

The experiments were conducted on the effect of constant prey densities on the biological parameters of adult female ladybird beetle. A total of 10 newly emerged adult female beetles of *H. dimidiata* were collected from stock culture and kept in ventilated plastic rearing jars (12X4 cm).

The beetle were provided constant densities (40, 80, 120, 160, 200 and 240), 3rd and 4th instar nymphs of *S. graminum* aphids daily in each jar on infested wheat leaves. Each prey density was repeated 10 times. Unmated male of similar ages were collected from the stock culture and were confined with 2 day old females in 1:1 ratio for 12 h to facilitate mating. This was repeated after each 48 h at the time of food change in order to uphold the reproductive vitality of female and the process was continued till their death. Individual gravid females of *H. dimidiata* were provided with constant prey densities of aphids daily inside the jars. The observations were carried out after each 24 hours. The data were recorded on the mean quantity of aphid's utilized (functional response) and the eggs produced (reproductive numerical response) and as well as growth rate of different stages of female beetles at constant prey densities for the entire life duration of female beetle. The data were recorded on the following parameters

- (i) Pre oviposition and oviposition period
- (ii) Female longevity
- (iii) Number of eggs per female
- (iv) Number of aphids consumed per female
- (v) Mean weight of female beetle

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed by Analysis of Variance one way (ANOVA) for interaction between the prey density and their effect on prey consumption rate, mean number of eggs produced, and developmental duration of immature and as well as adult female beetle. Comparison between different treatments was made by LSD test at significant level of 0.05. The data was analyzed by using Statistix 8.1 package. Regression lines of the functional and the reproductive response were drawn based on mean values of aphids consumed and eggs produced in relation to constant prey densities.

RESULTS

Effect of prey densities on the duration and weight of pre imaginal stages of *H. dimidiata* (fab.)

The developmental time and weight of various life phases of *H. dimidiata* with the provision of six host densities of *S. graminum* aphids was presented in (Table 1, 2). Influence of different prey density on the growth rate as well as weight of different immature stages was observed.

1st instar

The durations of first instar larvae were maximum (3.34 ± 0.12) days at low prey density (20 aphids/day) and minimum (2.47 ± 0.18) days at higher prey density of (120 aphids/day). The results showed that durations was significantly different at lower prey densities of (20 and 40 aphids/day) from other tested densities, while at higher densities the durations was non-significantly different from each other (Table 1). Similarly the weight of first instar larvae was maximum (1.69 ± 0.05) mg at prey density (100 aphids/day) and minimum (1.44 ± 0.11) mg at low density 20 aphids/day. The results showed that weight of first instar larvae was only significantly different at low density, while at the remaining density the weight was non significantly different from each other (Table 2).

2nd instar

The durations of second instar larvae were maximum (4.36 ± 0.14) days at low density (20 aphids/day), which was significantly different from all other tested densities. The results indicate that duration was none significantly different at higher prey densities (80, 100 and 120) aphids/day. The results further indicate that at prey densities (40 and 60 aphids/day), the durations were non-significantly different from each other but it was significantly different from all other tested densities (Table 1). The weight of 2nd instar larvae was maximum (9.58 ± 0.30) mg, when the larvae were provided 60 aphids/ day. The results showed that effect of prey density on weight of second instar larvae was only significantly different at low prey density, while at higher prey density it was non significantly different from each other (Table 2).

3rd instar

The durations of third instar larvae were maximum (7.80 ± 0.33) days at low prey density and minimum (4.20 ± 0.21) days, when 100 aphids /day were provided (Table 7.1). The results indicate that the duration of third instar larvae was significantly different at lower three prey densities including (20, 40 and 60 aphids/day), while it was non-significantly different at higher densities (80, 100 and 120 aphids /day (Table 1). The weight of third instar larvae was maximum (17.22 ± 0.39) mg at prey density 100 aphids per day and minimum (10.46 ± 0.55) mg at low prey density 20 aphids/day. The results indicate that the weight of third instar larvae were significantly different at lower densities including (20, 40 and 60) aphids/day while at higher prey densities (80, 100 and 120) aphids/day, the weight of 3rd instar larvae was non-significantly different from each other (Table 2).

4th instar

The durations of fourth instar larvae were maximum 36.60 ± 0.92 days at low prey density 20 aphids per day and minimum 8.40 ± 0.16 days at higher prey density 120 aphids per day. The results indicate that duration of fourth instar larvae was significantly different at all tested densities except at higher two densities 100 and 120 aphids per day, which was non-significantly dissimilar (Table 1).

The weight of fourth instar larvae was maximum 55.34 ± 0.86 mg and minimum 23.90 ± 0.75 mg at low prey density 20 aphids / day. The results indicates that prey density significantly affect the durations of fourth instar larvae except at higher two densities 100 and 120 aphids/ day, the weight of 4th instar was non-significantly different from each other (Table 2).

Larvae

The duration of larvae from (1st to 4th instar) was significantly different at all tested prey densities except at prey densities (100 and 120) aphids/day, at which the duration was non-significantly dissimilar (Table 7.1). Maximum duration of larvae was (52.10±0.64) days and minimum duration was (17.44±0.63) days at low and higher prey densities, when provided 20 and 120 aphids /day.

Pre pupal stage

The duration of pre pupal stage was maximum (1.82±0.10) days at low density 20 aphids per day and minimum (1.0±0.09) days at higher densities 120 aphids /day. Pre pupal duration was non-significantly unlike from each other except at low prey density 20 aphids/ day, which was significantly dissimilar from other densities (Table 7.1). The weight of pre pupal stage was maximum (37.4±1.26) mg at higher density when provided 80 aphids per day and minimum (22.60±0.34) mg at low density 20 aphids/day. The results indicate that at low prey densities the weight was significantly different while at higher prey densities (80, 100 and 120 aphids/day, it was non-significantly dissimilar from each other (Table 2).

Pupal stage

The duration of pupa was maximum (7.30±0.31) days at low density 20 aphids/day and minimum (5.0±0.08) days at higher density 120 aphids per day. The results indicate that the duration of pupae was significantly different at lower densities, when provided (20 and 40) aphids/day, while at the remaining higher densities the duration of pupae was non-significantly different (Table 1). The weight of pupae was maximum (33.6±0.34) mg when provided 80 aphids/day and minimum (19.80±0.44) mg at low density 20 aphids/day. The results indicates that weight of pupae was significantly different at all tested prey densities except at higher prey densities including (80, 100 and 120) aphids/ day, which was non-significantly unlike from each other (Table 2).

Duration from first instar to adult emergence

The durations from first instar to adult emergence was maximum (61.2±1.83) days at low density when provided 20 aphids/ day and minimum (23.2±0.83) days at higher prey density 120 aphids/ day. Duration from first instar to adult emergence was significantly unlike from each other at all tested prey densities except at higher prey densities 100 and 120 aphids/ day, (Table 1)

Biological attributes of adult female *H. dimidiata*(Fab.) in relation to constant prey densities

Pre oviposition period

The results showed that female *H. dimidiata* (Fab.) beetle could not reproduced eggs when provided 40 aphids/ day. The results indicate that duration of pre oviposition period was maximum (13.4±0.60) days at density (60) aphids /day and the duration was minimum (9.3±0.213) days at prey density (200) aphids /day. Pre oviposition period of female ladybird beetle was significantly unlike at lower prey densities including prey densities (80 and 120) aphids /day while at the remaining higher densities the duration was non-significantly unlike from each other (Table 3).

Oviposition period

The oviposition period of adult female beetle was maximum (42.2±0.59) at prey density (200) aphids /day and minimum was (21.7±0.99) days at prey density (80) aphids/day. The results showed that oviposition period was significantly different at all tested densities except at prey densities (200 and 240) aphids per day (Table 3).

Female beetle longevity

The adult female beetle longevity was maximum (58.2±0.61) days at higher prey density (200) aphids/day and minimum (24.5±1.42) days at low prey density when provided (40) aphids/day (Table 7.3). The results indicate that female longevity was significantly different from each other at all tested prey densities except at higher prey densities (200) and (240) aphids per day (Table 7.3). The results showed that initially the developmental duration increase with increasing prey density up to prey density 200 aphids/ day and then further increase in prey density have no significant upshot on the longevity of adult female beetle (Table 3)

Female fecundity

The female fecundity rate in relation six constant prey densities showed maximum (678.2±6.33) eggs per

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female when provided 200 aphids /day and minimum (316.80±2.901) eggs when provided 80 aphids /day. The results further indicate that female could not produce eggs at extreme low density, when they were provided (40) aphids per day. The results indicate that female fecundity was significantly different at different densities except at higher prey densities including 200 and 240 aphids /day (Table 3 and Fig. 6.) Once the female get maximum level then further increase in prey density has no significant effect on the fecundity rate. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is a superiorly fit to the feeding data $y = -297.9 + 8.707x - 0.019x^2$, $r^2 = 0.988$. The results showed density dependent fecundity of female beetle ladybird beetle with increasing prey density the fecundity increase. At prey density 200 aphids/ day the female produced maximum eggs, once the asymptote level attain, then further increase in prey density has no significant effect on the fecundity rate but decrease occurs at maximum prey density (Fig. 6)

Weight of female ladybird beetle

The results indicate that weight of female ladybird beetle was maximum (66.12±1.78) mg when provided 200 aphids / day and minimum (37.94±0.80) mg when provided 40 aphids /day. The results indicate that weight of female beetle was significantly different at lower prey densities and it was non-significant different at higher prey densities including (160, 200 and 240) aphids per day (Table 2).

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Table 1: Effect of prey densities on developmental duration (days) $\pm$ SE of immature stages of *H. dimidiata*, fed on *S. graminum* aphid

Developmental stage	Prey density						LSD $P \leq 0.05$)
	20	40	60	80	100	120	
	Durations $\pm$ SE						
1 st instar	3.34 $\pm$ 0.12a	2.97 $\pm$ 0.16b	2.59 $\pm$ 0.16bc	2.54 $\pm$ 0.16bc	2.53 $\pm$ 0.15bc	2.47 $\pm$ 0.18c	0.4440
2 nd instar	4.36 $\pm$ 0.14a	3.78 $\pm$ 0.24b	3.30 $\pm$ 0.21b	2.63 $\pm$ 0.21c	2.29 $\pm$ 0.11c	2.27 $\pm$ 0.11c	0.5094
3 rd instar	7.80 $\pm$ 0.33a	6.40 $\pm$ 0.34b	5.10 $\pm$ 0.34c	4.30 $\pm$ 0.10d	4.20 $\pm$ 0.21d	4.30 $\pm$ 0.25d	0.7187
4 th instar	36.60 $\pm$ 0.92a	27.20 $\pm$ 0.79b	20.50 $\pm$ 0.82c	11.90 $\pm$ 0.82d	8.60 $\pm$ 0.31e	8.40 $\pm$ 0.16e	1.7690
Larva	52.10 $\pm$ 0.64a	40.35 $\pm$ 0.66b	31.49 $\pm$ 0.56c	21.37 $\pm$ 0.33d	17.62 $\pm$ 0.65e	17.44 $\pm$ 0.63e	1.6718
Pre pupal stage	1.82 $\pm$ 0.10a	1.25 $\pm$ 0.13b	1.07 $\pm$ 0.05b	1.0 $\pm$ 0.08b	1.00 $\pm$ 0.08b	1.0 $\pm$ 0.09b	0.2600
Pupa	7.30 $\pm$ 0.30a	6.10 $\pm$ 0.35b	5.50 $\pm$ 0.17bc	5.30 $\pm$ 0.15c	5.30 $\pm$ 0.17c	5.00 $\pm$ 0.08c	0.6295
1 st instar to adult emergence	61.20 $\pm$ 1.83a	47.70 $\pm$ 1.83b	38.10 $\pm$ 0.82c	27.60 $\pm$ 0.97d	23.40 $\pm$ 0.91e	23.20 $\pm$ 0.83e	3.4316

Means with different lower case letters rows wise are significantly different from each other at P value ≤ 0.05 (One-way ANOVA) using LSD test.

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Table 2: Effect of prey densities on the mean weight ($\pm$ SE) of different stages of *H. dimidiata* (Fab.), fed on *S. graminum* aphid

Developmental stage	Prey density						LSD $P \leq 0.05$)
	20	40	60	80	100	120	
	Mean weight $\pm$ SE						
1 st instar	1.44 $\pm$ 0.11b	1.68 $\pm$ 0.04a	1.64 $\pm$ 0.04a	1.67 $\pm$ 0.04a	1.69 $\pm$ 0.05a	1.68 $\pm$ 0.06a	0.17
2 nd instar	7.58 $\pm$ 0.42b	8.70 $\pm$ 0.37ab	9.58 $\pm$ 0.30a	9.51 $\pm$ 0.51a	9.45 $\pm$ 0.61a	9.44 $\pm$ 0.27a	1.22
3 rd instar	10.46 $\pm$ 0.55d	12.35 $\pm$ 0.31c	14.56 $\pm$ 0.25b	17.22 $\pm$ 0.39a	17.06 $\pm$ 0.41a	17.10 $\pm$ 0.41a	1.13
4 th instar	23.90 $\pm$ 0.75e	29.90 $\pm$ 1.10d	44.90 $\pm$ 0.91c	51.10 $\pm$ 1.27b	55.34 $\pm$ 0.86a	54.80 $\pm$ 0.93a	2.79
Pre pupal stage	22.60 $\pm$ 0.34d	26.60C $\pm$ 1.32c	32.10 $\pm$ 1.49b	37.40 $\pm$ 1.26a	34.90 $\pm$ 1.55ab	35.70 $\pm$ 0.82a	3.42
Pupa	19.80 $\pm$ 0.44d	24.70 $\pm$ 0.76c	28.80 $\pm$ 1.07b	33.60 $\pm$ 0.34a	33.10 $\pm$ 0.72a	33.0 $\pm$ 0.84a	2.09
Female beetle	37.94 $\pm$ 0.80d	46.70 $\pm$ 1.41c	55.13 $\pm$ 1.59b	64.68 $\pm$ 1.42a	66.12 $\pm$ 1.78a	65.82 $\pm$ 1.58a	4.15

Means with different lower case letters rows wise are significantly different from each other at P value ≤ 0.05 (One-way ANOVA) using LSD test

Table 3: Effect of prey densities on the biological attributes of adult female *H. dimidiata*, fed on *S. graminum* aphid

Developmental stage	Pre densities						LSD $P \leq 0.05$)
	40	80	120	160	200	240	
	Durations (days) $\pm$ SE	Durations (days) $\pm$ SE	Durations $\pm$ SE	Durations $\pm$ SE	Durations $\pm$ SE	Durations $\pm$ SE	
Pre oviposition period	0.000	13.40 $\pm$ 0.60a	11.40 $\pm$ 0.22b	10.00 $\pm$ 0.30c	9.30 $\pm$ 0.21c	9.60 $\pm$ 0.27c	0.91
Oviposition period	0.000	21.70 $\pm$ 0.99d	29.90 $\pm$ 0.88c	36.60 $\pm$ 1.05b	42.20 $\pm$ 0.59a	41.30 $\pm$ 0.70a	2.22
Female longevity	24.50 $\pm$ 1.42d	42.10 $\pm$ 1.27c	52.40 $\pm$ 1.25b	54.80 $\pm$ 0.94b	57.90 $\pm$ 0.59a	58.20 $\pm$ 0.61a	3.02
Female fecundity	0.0 $\pm$ 0.00	316.80 $\pm$ 2.90d	448.60 $\pm$ 12.83c	564.6B $\pm$ 13.31b	678.2 $\pm$ 6.33a	657.4 $\pm$ 7.82a	24.59
Mean aphids consumed/female/day	36.40 $\pm$ 0.93e	71.40 $\pm$ 2.33d	105.80 $\pm$ 2.80c	136.60 $\pm$ 4.27b	146.80 $\pm$ 4.37a	143.60A $\pm$ 2.10a	8.66

Means with different lower case letters rows wise are significantly different from each other at P value ≤ 0.05 (One-way ANOVA) using LSD test.

Effect of prey densities on the predatory potential of larval instars and adult female *H. dimidiata* (Fab.)

1st instar larvae

The predatory potential of 1st instar larvae in relation to six constant prey densities indicate that the potential was significantly different at lower two densities 20 and 40 aphids/ day from all other tested densities. The prey consumption potential was maximum 32.3 ± 0.42 and minimum 17.4 ± 0.37 aphids per day (Fig 1). The results indicate that with increasing prey density the number of consumed aphids increases up to prey density 60 aphids/ day. The results indicate that first instar larvae attain asymptote level at prey density 60 aphids/ day, above this density further increase in prey density have no significant effect on prey consumption capacity of first instar larvae. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is a good fit to the feeding data $Y = -0.003x^2 + 0.545x + 8.27$, $r^2 = 0.954$. The polynomial fit was drawn which indicate that initial increase in prey densities increase the prey consumption capacity and after attain the asymptote level then further increase in prey density have no significant effect on prey consumption. The first instar larvae exhibit type II functional response in which the tempo of prey utilization by the predator goes up as the prey population enhances, but ultimately levels off at plateau or asymptote at which the rate of utilization become stable (Fig. 1).

2nd instar larvae

The predatory potential of 2nd instar larvae in relation to constant prey densities showed that the prey consumption capacity was significantly different at low prey densities 20 and 40 aphids /day from higher prey densities. The prey consumption potential was maximum (47.8 ± 1.84) and minimum (18.2 ± 0.51) aphids per day (Fig. 2). The results showed that with increasing prey density the consumption capacity increase up to prey density 60 aphids/ day (Fig 7.2). The results indicate that as in first instar larvae attained asymptote level at prey density 60 aphids/ day, again in second instar larvae the asymptote level was attained when provided 60 aphids / day. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is a good fit to the feeding data, $y = -0.74 + 1.093x - 0.005x^2$, $r^2 = 0.953$, ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 7.2). Once attain the asymptote level then further increase in prey density has no significant effect on prey consumption rate. The second instar larvae also exhibit type II functional response, in which the speed of prey utilization by the predator increases as the prey density goes up, but finally levels off at asymptote at which the rate of utilization remain invariable (Fig 2).

3rd instar larvae

The Predatory potential of 3rd instar larvae in relation to constant prey densities showed that at low prey densities (20, 40 and 60) aphids/ day, the prey consumption capacity was significantly different from higher prey densities. The prey consumption potential was maximum (51.7 ± 0.93) and minimum (19.2 ± 0.20) aphids per day (Fig. 3). The results showed that with increasing prey density the consumption capacity increase. The results indicate that the 3rd instar larvae attain asymptote level at prey density when provided 80 aphids /day. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is a good fit to the feeding data $y = -0.58 + 1.011x - 0.004x^2$, $r^2 = 0.978$, (Fig. 3). The results further showed that once the larvae attain the asymptote levels, then further increase in prey densities have no significant effect on the predatory potential. The 3rd instar larvae also exhibit type II functional response (Fig. 3).

4th instar larvae

The Predatory potential of 4th instar larvae in relation to constant prey densities showed that predatory potential of 4th instar larvae was significantly different at different prey density except at higher two densities including 100 and 120 aphids/ day (Fig. 4). The prey consumption potential was maximum (74.1 ± 1.14) and minimum (19.3 ± 0.34) aphids per day (Fig.4). The results showed that with increasing prey density the consumption capacity increase up to prey density 100 aphids/ day. The results indicate that the larvae attained asymptote level at prey density 100 aphids/ day. The results further indicate that once the larvae attain the asymptote level further increase in prey density have no significant effect on prey consumption capacity of larvae. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is a good fit to the feeding data $y = -5.04 + 1.212x - 0.004x^2$, $r^2 = 0.986$, ($P < 0.05$: Fig. 4). The 4th instar larvae also exhibit type II functional response as in earlier instars (Fig. 4).

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Adult female ladybird beetle

The Predatory potential of adult female ladybird beetle in relation to six constant prey densities was significantly different at different prey density except at higher two densities including (200 and 240) aphids/ day (Fig. 5). The prey consumption potential was maximum (146.8 ±4.37) and minimum (36.4±0.93) aphids/day, when provided 200 and Only 40 aphids/ day (Fig. 5). The adult female attains asymptote level when provided 200 aphids/ day. The results further indicate that once the female beetle attain the asymptote level than further increase in prey density have no significant effect on prey consumption capacity of female adybird beetle. Regression analysis suggested that a curvilinear response is the best fit to the feeding data $y = -20.5 + 1.465x - 0.003x^2$, $r^2 = 0.991$, (Fig. 5). The adult female beetle also exhibit type II functional response as in larval instars, in which the tempo of prey utilization by the predator goes up as the prey density increase, but in due course levels off at asymptote at which the rate of utilization remain invariable (Fig. 5)

Fig. 1: Polynomial fit for number of prey eaten against number of prey offered by 1st instar larva

Fig. 2: Polynomial fit for number of prey eaten against number of prey offered by 2nd instar larva

Fig. 3: Polynomial fit for number of prey eaten against number of prey offered by 3rd instar larva

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Fig. 4 Polynomial fit for number of prey eaten against number of prey offered by 4th instar larva

Fig. 6 Polynomial fit for mean number of eggs produced by female *H. dimidiata* in relation to constant prey densities

DISCUSSION

The preceding section describes the outcome of different prey densities on the biological attributes and predatory efficiency of *H. dimidiata*, reared on suitable host *S. graminum* aphid at optimum temperature 24 ± 1 °C. Density dependent developmental duration and predatory potential was observed. The durations of immature and adult stages was maximum at lower prey density levels and with increasing prey densities the developmental durations of different stages significantly decreased. But the duration, weight and prey

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consumption potential was non-significantly different at higher densities. Once the particular stage attains the asymptote level than further increase in prey density have no significant effect on the duration, weight and predatory potential. Although *H. dimidiata* was least studied species in this regards, but comprehensive work was carried out in the past on other Coccinellid beetles. Our results are in conformity with Soodeh *et al.* (2013), who reported that the durations of different stages of *Hippodamia variegata* when feed on different densities of *A. gossypii*, significantly decreased with increasing prey density. Similarly Sharmila *et al.* (2010), reported that duration of larvae of *H. dimidiata* decreased with increasing prey density, when fed on *Cervaphis quercus* aphid. During the course of the present study although the larvae successfully completed their development at lowest prey density level and relative increase in weight was observed with increasing prey density. It may be ascribed to the fact that predacious Coccinellids show a prominent capability to regulate to food shortage as an adaptation to sporadic lack of prey. Hodek and Honek (1996) reported that larvae of *Coccinella septempunctata* could complete its development when food was artificially condensed to 55 or 40 percent. During the course of the present study similar effect was observed on the duration and reproductive potential of adult female ladybird beetle in relation to prey densities. During the course of the present study female could not produce eggs at lowest prey density. The results showed that at lower prey densities the duration of pre oviposition and oviposition period was significantly different and at higher prey densities the duration was non significantly different. Our results are in conformation with Agarwala *et al.* (2009) that at lower prey density the oviposition period of *H. dimidiata* was significantly different from higher densities and female could not produce eggs at low density 20 aphids. Female maintained at lower prey densities had a shorter life span than female kept at higher prey densities. The female fecundity was significantly different in relation to different prey densities and with increasing prey density the fecundity rate increase accordingly. At prey density (200 aphids /day) the female produced maximum eggs and further increase in prey density have non-significant effect on fecundity of female beetle. The reproductive numerical response and functional response of *H. dimidiata* was similar. The shape of functional and reproductive numerical response is evocative of the reliance of the predator rate of rise on their successful consumption of prey. The results of the present study indicate significant influence of prey density on the reproductive attributes in term of egg production. The predatory potential of different larval instars in relation to different prey density showed, initially rapid increase in prey consumption with gradual decrease at higher prey densities. The asymptote levels for 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th instars larvae was at prey densities 60, 60, 80 and 100 aphids/ day at which they performed their best and consumed maximum aphids/day. The functional response of different larval instars in relation to different prey density revealed an initial rapid increase in prey consumption with a gradual decrease at higher prey density. An optimum response was different for different larval instar according to their capacity in relation to different prey density. The functional response exhibited by the first, second, third and fourth instars larvae exemplified type II predatory response as described by Holling (1959) as that in the type II functional response, rate of prey utilization by the predator goes up as the prey density goes up, but in due course levels off at asymptote at which the rate of utilization remain invariable in spite of rise in prey density. Different workers reported in the past type II functional response in different Coccinellid beetles. i.e. Agarwala *et al.* (2009), Omkar and Pervez (2005), Soodeh *et al.* (2013) reported type II functional response in different Coccinellid beetles feeding on different aphid species. Such a response is distinctive of predators feeding in non-established prey densities and this response means quick use of food by predators even at lower prey populations. The above findings are similar to those of Agarwala and Bardhanroy (1997), Agarwala *et al.*, (2001) reported an increased aphid prey resulted in longer pre reproductive periods. Longer reproductive periods of females accompanied by higher fecundity was recorded at 200 aphids per day which might be ascribed to optimum consumption and utilization of aphid food that provide adequate energy for maturation of eggs over a longer period. Lower prey density might have affected the eggs production and maturations. Ferran *et al.* (1984) recorded a linear association in amount of food eaten and number of eggs laid. Feeding and oviposition model of single predator reveal the adaptation of their populations to feeding conditions in the fields (Agarwala and Bhattacharya, 1995; Dixon, 2000). As an outcome at any moment, the number of aphids accessible in area as food for predators may differ. In those situation predators capable to adjust to uneven food resources will have superior impact on prey population.

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